

UNLOCKING DATA

Canada

DESIGN-BASED IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH REPORT: CYCLE 2

SCALING DATA USE IN SUBNATIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEMS IN KENYA

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About the Unlocking Data Initiative

The Unlocking Data Initiative is a community of practice that connects African scholars, NGOs, national statistics offices, and policymakers to improve access to and use of education data. The **Unlocking Data: Scaling Uses and Users of Education Data** project is a collaborative effort led by Mizizi Elimu Afrika Foundation (formerly Zizi Afrique Foundation) and supported by Education Sub-Saharan Africa, eBase Africa, and University of Malawi's Centre for Education Research and Training (CERT). The latter project, which is being implemented in Cameroon, Kenya and Malawi, aims to scale up the use and users of data to address the knowledge gap of how to adaptively scale up the effective use of existing education data by policymakers and researchers in Africa.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CECM	County Executive Committee Member
CERT	Centre for Education Research and Training
CoG	Council of Governors
DBIR	Design-Based Implementation Research
ECDE	Early Childhood Development and Education
SCDE	Subcounty Director of Education
TWG	Technical Working Group
UDI	Unlocking Data Initiative

Executive summary

This report presents findings from Cycle 2 of the Design-Based Implementation Research (DBIR) work under the Unlocking Data Initiative, which aims to enhance and expand data use in subnational education systems across Kenya. Building on Cycle 1, which tested and demonstrated an early proof of concept in Marsabit County, Cycle 2 focused on institutionalising data practices, scaling them across multiple counties, and addressing systemic challenges to ensure sustainability.

During Cycle 2, the initiative expanded to four additional counties: Kirinyaga, Kajiado, Nairobi, and Kisumu, drawing on lessons from Marsabit and adapting them to the specific contexts of those counties. The DBIR approach emphasises co-creation and validation, the use of locally relevant data, organised engagement platforms, and step-by-step demonstrations of data value through an iterative learning-implementation-feedback loop.

During Cycle 2, the report highlights the following early achievements:

- Increased consistency, through attendance at subnational meetings, has improved.
- Incorporation of data aspects into institutional structures established in Cycle 1.
- Formal nomination of data officers (champions) in the counties
- Emerging evidence-based decision-making, including:
 - Water mapping in Marsabit County;
 - ECDE teacher deployment and allocation of teaching and learning materials in Kirinyaga;
- Growing interest from additional counties in strengthening data capacity.

However, three critical challenges persist:

1. Dashboard hosting and technical ownership constraints
2. Fragility of data use culture amid competing priorities
3. High turnover among trained subnational officers and data champions

The DBIR Cycle 2 focused on ensuring that sustainable county-level data use addresses the technical issues, but also systems and behaviour change. UDI sought to integrate data use into institutional structures, rather than relying on individual champions; this is crucial for achieving lasting impact.

1. Context for the DBIR

1.1. Background

The Unlocking Data Initiative's Design-Based Implementation Research (DBIR) work in Kenya is fundamentally concerned with changing how subnational education officers relate to data: shifting it from a compliance obligation collected for the Ministry of Education into a working resource that county officers actively generate, interpret, and apply to their own administrative decisions. This change matters because Kenya's foundational learning ecosystem suffers not from a lack of data but from a persistent disconnection between what is collected and what is used, a gap driven by organisational, systemic, technical, and legal barriers that prevent evidence from flowing back to the local actors best positioned to act on it.

Cycle 1 tested this proposition as a prototype in Marsabit County, demonstrating that county officers could be brought to a basic level of data awareness and capacity, while also surfacing three structural vulnerabilities that limited how far that early progress could travel: data capacity that depended on specific individuals rather than institutional roles, a data-use culture treated as a project activity rather than a routine practice, and a technical infrastructure that counties could access, but neither owned nor maintained ([↑Gachoki et al., 2025](#)).

Cycle 2 builds directly on this prototype by carrying its lessons into four additional counties, Kirinyaga, Kajiado, Nairobi, and Kisumu, while deliberately reorienting the programme's focus from demonstrating that data use is possible to embedding it so that it can survive staff turnover, compete successfully against other institutional priorities, and operate on infrastructure that counties can sustain themselves. This shift toward institutionalisation, rather than continued piloting, reflects a judgment that the central risk to the programme's long-term impact is not technical but structural: data practices that remain dependent on motivated individuals and externally managed systems will not scale or endure, however successful they prove within a single cycle or county.

1.2. State of foundational learning data in Kenya

Kenya's foundational learning ecosystem is characterised by a significant imbalance between data availability and data use. A situational analysis conducted by UDI in 2025 ([↑Gachoki & Arisa, 2025](#)) mapped the foundational learning data and knowledge ecosystem in Kenya, with a companion Evidence Gap Map ([↑Arisa & Gachoki, 2025](#)) that identified clusters and gaps in the existing evidence base. Together, the two outputs found that the Ministry of Education and its departments collect and store considerable data on foundational learning. However, the flow of this data within and beyond the government system is deeply constrained.

This matters for county-level decision-making because data that is collected but not analysed or returned to local actors has little value for the decisions county officers have to make.

The situational analysis identified four categories of barriers that constrain the flow of evidence across the ecosystem: organisational, systemic, technical, and legal. Organisational barriers include a culture of working in silos, institutional reluctance to share data, and the absence of systematic dissemination mechanisms. Systemic barriers include a lack of trust between state and non-state actors, complex power imbalances, and a tendency for policymakers to selectively use data that supports pre-existing decisions rather than drawing on a broad evidence base. Technical barriers relate to challenges of data quality, security, and privacy. Legal barriers include limitations under the Data Protection Act, which restricts data sharing beyond its intended scope to personal data.

A particularly significant finding from the situational analysis is that subnational officers may view data as information collected for the Ministry of Education rather than as a resource for their own administrative use. This disposition can undermine the demand for county-level data and may lead to the submission of inaccurate or estimated figures, rendering the data unsuitable for the evidence-based decision-making it is intended to support.

1.3. The role of the Design-Based Implementation Research approach

In response to these systemic challenges, UDI adopted a Design-Based Implementation Research (DBIR) approach as its primary implementation framework ([↑Waziri, 2026](#)). DBIR runs short cycles of design, implementation, and reflection, with evidence from each cycle feeding into the design of the next ([↑Fishman et al., 2013](#); [↑Penuel et al., 2011](#)). This makes it well-suited to the complex, context-dependent challenges of building a data culture within sub-national government systems.

The DBIR process is organised into cycles, each designed around specific strategic objectives informed by the findings of the previous cycle. Cycle 1 ([↑Gachoki et al., 2025](#)) focused on building foundational awareness of data use among county officers and piloting early approaches to capacity strengthening. It identified three structural challenges that would require deeper attention in subsequent cycles:

1. The vulnerability of data capacity to staff turnover;
2. The fragility of data-use culture as a project-specific rather than institutionally embedded practice; and
3. The dependence of county data systems on externally managed infrastructure that counties lacked the capacity to own and maintain.

1.4. DBIR Cycle 2 objectives

Building directly on these findings, Cycle 2 shifted the programme's focus from experimentation and awareness-raising to institutionalisation and scaling.

The following three specific objectives for DBIR Cycle 2 reflect the initiative's focus on scaling, institutionalisation, and addressing systemic challenges.

Objective 1: To establish sustainable data-use structures by shifting from dependence on individual champions to formally integrated, role-based data positions within county governments.

This objective directly addresses the critical evidence-to-practice disconnect caused by high turnover among trained personnel. Moving beyond the “revolving door” problem identified in Cycle 1, the goal is to embed data-use practices within the formal structures of county governments. Rather than relying on specific individuals, this objective aims to establish durable mechanisms. Key result areas include formalising designated data officer roles with documented job descriptions, creating standing Technical Working Groups (TWGs) with clear terms of reference, and developing standardised handover protocols and onboarding materials to maintain continuity despite staff changes.

Objective 2: To enhance evidence-based decision-making by incorporating data usage into existing county governance and planning processes, with progress tracked through specific examples of data informing administrative decisions.

This objective addresses systemic challenges in data use by shifting data activities from marginal, project-specific efforts to the centre of routine government operations. The emphasis is on integration rather than adding new activities. Success under this objective is measured not by how well data informs key administrative processes, but by the number of dashboards. The aim is to make this the standard practice, ensuring that data becomes a normal input for annual work plans, budget discussions, and regular review meetings.

Objective 3: To improve decentralised data ownership and its usefulness by overcoming technical infrastructure limitations and focusing on locally relevant, actionable data products.

This objective directly addresses shifting counties away from reliance on externally managed, complex systems towards stronger ownership. The goal is data systems that counties control and maintain themselves, not just systems they can access. The objective is pursued through two complementary moves. First, matching technical solutions to local capacity, including low-tech offline tools such as printed data briefs, where county hosting is infeasible. Second, ensuring that the data flowing through these systems is locally generated and contextually relevant; the common literacy and numeracy assessment is one such application. Success under this objective means at

least one county progressing from dashboard appreciation to documented hosting and maintenance arrangements managed by county staff or county-contracted vendors.

Cycle 2 also marked an important broadening of the programme's engagement at the national level, with Ministry of Education officials and the Council of Governors brought into the dialogue to ensure that subnational data work is reinforced by, rather than operating separately from, national policy and governance frameworks. This alignment between national and subnational actors is a critical enabler for the long-term sustainability and scale of the initiative's outcomes.

1.5. Scope of the DBIR

Building on the foundational work of DBIR Cycle 1, where we piloted the collection and visualisation of data through an interactive dashboard, we demonstrated the feasibility of strengthening data use in subnational education systems. Cycle 2 focused on scaling, institutionalisation, and sustainability. While the initial phase established that data-informed decision-making is both possible and valuable, it also revealed critical structural and systemic constraints that must be addressed to sustain and expand impact.

This second cycle builds on lessons learned from implementation in Marsabit County and investigates how these lessons have been adapted and replicated across Kirinyaga, Kajiado, Nairobi, and Kisumu counties. The aim is to shift from isolated successes driven by individual actors to county-level systems that foster consistent, resilient, and locally owned data-use practices.

1.5.1. Design of DBIR Cycle 2

The central design question that guided DBIR Cycle 2 was: How can county governments institutionalise the use of data for decision-making in ways they can sustain over time?

To address this, Cycle 2 is anchored on four key design principles. First, there is a deliberate shift from individual-driven to system-driven approaches, ensuring that data use practices are embedded within institutional structures rather than reliant on specific individuals. Second, the approach emphasises decentralised data ownership, allowing counties to generate, analyse, and use their own data. Third, data use is integrated into existing decision-making cycles rather than treated as a separate activity. Finally, the approach prioritises the continuous demonstration of value through incremental gains, building stakeholder confidence and maintaining engagement.

1.6. Report structure

This report is organised into six sections.

Section 1 provides the context of the DBIR approach and the objectives that guided Cycle 2.

Section 2 outlines the methodology, including the activities conducted during the cycle, the participants involved in data collection, and the limitations to consider when interpreting the findings.

Section 3 presents the key findings and insights emerging from implementation across the five participating counties, organised around the three strategic objectives of Cycle 2.

Section 4 distils the most significant lessons learned and proposes concrete adaptations to strengthen programme design in subsequent cycles.

Section 5 maps each finding to its contribution toward the programme's long-term outcome of scaling sustainable data use within county government systems.

Section 6 presents the conclusion and priority next steps recommended for Cycle 3 and a list of references is provided in Section 7.

2. Methodology

This section sets out how the findings and insights in this report were generated; the key activities undertaken during Cycle 2; the participants who contributed to data collection; and the limitations to consider when interpreting the evidence. The methodology was primarily qualitative, centred on key informant interviews (KIIs) with county data officers across five participating counties. A qualitative approach was selected because the programme’s core questions at this stage relate to how and why change is occurring within county governance systems, not only what has changed. The interviews were complemented by a review of programme documents, workshop reports, and county-level data products generated during the cycle, which were used to triangulate interview claims where possible. The limitations outlined in section 2.3 are acknowledged transparently and provide the necessary interpretive boundaries within which the evidence should be read.

2.1. Activities completed during DBIR cycle 2

Cycle 2 shifted the focus from experimentation to institutionalisation and scale. The activities in this cycle included bringing the Ministry officers and the Council of Governors to the discussion table. This is to ensure that subnational-level work is reinforced rather than treated as a separate activity.

2.2. Participants

Key informant interviews were conducted between 26th and 27th January 2026, involving data officers (champions) from Kirinyaga, Kisumu, Marsabit, Nairobi and Kajiado. The participants comprised 10 County officers (5 Male and 5 Female).

Table 1. Key informant interviews

County	Male	Female	Total
Kirinyaga		2	2
Kajiado	2		2
Marsabit	1	1	2
Nairobi		1	1
Kisumu	1	1	2
Council of Governors	1		1
Total	5	5	10

2.3. Limitations

The following four limitations bound how the evidence in this report should be read.

2.3.1. Self-reporting bias

Data collected through key informant interviews is subject to social desirability bias, whereby respondents may present their counties' progress in a more favourable light than the evidence on the ground fully supports. In the absence of direct observation or independent verification of reported practices, some findings may reflect aspirational rather than fully embedded practice; where possible, interview claims have been cross-checked against programme documents and county data products generated during the cycle (see Section 2 introduction)

2.3.2. Programme cycle constraints

The findings reflect the status of implementation at a specific point in time. Preliminary outcomes and indicators should therefore be read as early signals of progress rather than definitive assessments of the programme's impact.

2.3.3. Attribution challenges

In complex governance environments, isolating the contribution of the Unlocking Data Initiative from other concurrent interventions, including national government programmes, donor-funded projects, and county-level initiatives, is methodologically difficult. Where positive changes in data-use practices are observed, it is not always possible to attribute them exclusively to the programme's activities, and the report does not claim the exclusive attribution.

2.3.4. Sample size and scope

Thirteen interviews, concentrated in five counties, constitute a modest evidence base for the institutional-change conclusions drawn in this report. The sample also includes only county-level data officers; senior leadership (CECMs, County Directors), finance officers, school heads, and external stakeholders were not interviewed. The leadership-as-catalyst finding (Sections 3.1 and 5.1) in particular draws on what data officers observed about their seniors, rather than on what senior leaders themselves reported. Future cycles would benefit from a wider participant base.

3. Key findings and insights

This section presents three findings from Cycle 2, each corresponding to one of the strategic objectives. The picture shows progress in some counties, from awareness of data use to early institutional uptake, with substantial variation across sites. Where progress has occurred, it has been uneven, and the section is candid about both. The three findings below are structured around the three strategic objectives that guided Cycle 2. Each finding draws on evidence from implementation across the five counties and, where available, on direct quotation from county officials. The objectives were a priori; the section headings emerged inductively from the interviews and are noted alongside the objectives they address.

3.1. Leadership as the catalyst

Counties that made significant strides under this objective were those where senior officials actively championed role formalisation (Kirinyaga-SCDE, Marasabit-SCDE, Kajiado-Director ECDE, Kisumu-SCDE), treating it not as an administrative exercise but as a strategic investment in institutional resilience. Conversely, in Nairobi, where formalisation was driven primarily at the technical officer level without visible endorsement from senior leadership, progress was slower, and the resulting structures remained more vulnerable to reversal or neglect.

Stakeholder reflections underscored both the value of this shift and the continued effort required to sustain it. Kirinyaga, Marsabit, and Kisumu have formally recognised a data officer role, and county officials in these three counties noted that this changed the internal dynamic: data requests were directed to a specific person with a defined mandate, rather than falling to whoever happened to have the technical skills at the time. Kajiado and Nairobi, by contrast, have not established an equivalent role, and in these two counties, requests take longer to process, with no designated point of responsibility to move them along. The contrast between the three counties and the two suggests that formalising the role, not merely having staff capable of producing data, is what determines whether requests are handled promptly.

“The Unlocking Data Initiative has been instrumental in capacity building for my team (Government official, ECDE).”

The most important constraint observed across the cycle is that data officer job descriptions, where they exist, are not yet formally adopted into county HR establishment frameworks. Until they are, the positions remain fragile and dependent on the goodwill of incumbent leadership. Cycle 3 will need to prioritise gazettelement and inclusion in county staff establishment registers (see Section 6.2.1).

3.2. Adoption of a data culture

To address the fragile data-use culture identified in Cycle 1, the UDI focused on shifting data activities from the margins of county work to the centre of routine operations. The emphasis was on integration rather than on adding new activities. Success under this objective was measured by how well data, particularly data beyond the routine indicators, counties already report to inform key administrative processes upward.

After capacity-focused activities were completed, three county-led data exercises illustrate what the shift looked like in practice.

In Kisumu, officers collected school land-ownership data, particularly title deeds, which are required for the registration of standalone ECDE centres. Of 31 standalone ECDEs surveyed, one lacked a title deed, and another operated on rented premises; both were referred for follow-up action by the County. In Kirinyaga, officers used enrolment data to recruit and deploy ECDE teachers; the data informed deployment decisions for teachers across ECDE centres during the cycle. In Marsabit, the county conducted a water status survey across 30 schools to identify those requiring water scarcity interventions. Only four schools were found to be water-sufficient, and the data have been used to prioritise. In each case, the data was generated locally, in response to a problem the officer was already accountable for, and was used to inform a concrete administrative decision.

In Kajiado, the County Director of Education formally raised the need to strengthen the data and analytical capacity of education officers within the Education Technical Working Group (TWG). The TWG endorsed the request, and additional officers were nominated for UDI capacity building. In this sequence, the CDE raises the need, the TWG endorses, and the county acts as the institutional pattern the UDI is seeking to make standard across counties.

3.3. Genuine ownership

The issue of dashboard hosting and technical ownership constraints was found to affect the dashboard's sustainability and, hence, the data-use culture established thereon. It was also identified that some Counties, such as Kirinyaga, rely on contracted ICT personnel; hence, the expected continuous technical backstopping cannot be assured.

4. Lessons learned, and adaptations proposed

The implementation of Cycle 2 generated insights that extend beyond measuring outputs and outcomes. As the UDI matures, the experiences of participating counties, their progress and their constraints offer a critical body of evidence for strengthening programme design in subsequent cycles. This section distils the most significant lessons from Cycle 2 across the three strategic objectives and proposes concrete adaptations for Cycle 3.

The lessons presented here are a product of a programme operating in complex, resource-constrained sub-national governance environments, where implementation surfaces realities that design cannot fully anticipate. Each lesson is paired with a concrete adaptation proposed for Cycle 3.

4.1. Leverage champions as peer influencers across counties

Peer influence outperforms top-down technical guidance in driving institutional formalisation. Senior officials and data officers appointed in counties where formalisation succeeded should be identified as peer champions and engaged in cross-county learning exchanges. Governor-level or County Executive Committee Member (CECM)-level testimony carries institutional weight that programme staff cannot replicate, and horizontal peer influence has proven more persuasive than vertical technical guidance in comparable governance-strengthening programmes ([Andrews et al., 2017](#)).

Adaptation for Cycle 3: Establish a structured peer champion network that convenes CECM- and director-level officials from high-performing counties for facilitated cross-county learning exchanges, designed as working sessions rather than showcase events. (See Section 6.2.2 for the operational detail.)

4.2. Data culture takes root when data solves problems officers already own.

Data culture does not shift because officers are told it should, or even because they are trained in new skills. It shifts when new practices visibly reduce the burden of existing responsibilities or improve the quality of decisions for which officers are already accountable. The three case studies in Section 3.2, title-deed data in Kisumu, enrolment data in Kirinyaga, water-status data in Marsabit, illustrate this pattern: in each case, data became compelling because it answered a question the officer was already accountable for, not because the programme asked the officer to use data

Adaptation for Cycle 3: Map county administrative calendars at the start of the cycle to identify when data is most likely to be useful (e.g., work plans, budget consultations, departmental reviews), and align data collection and analysis activities with those

moments. Develop a core set of replicable use cases drawn from Cycle 2 for counties where data culture is still emerging. (See Section 6.2.3 for the operational detail.)

4.3. Explore tiered hosting arrangements at the subnational level, where individual county hosting is not feasible.

A recurring and critical observation across counties was the disconnect between officers' recognition of the value of established dashboards and their practical ability to host, maintain, and operate them independently. Officers consistently expressed appreciation for what the dashboards offered: accessible visualisation of complex data, a basis for evidence-informed discussions, and a tangible demonstration of what data use could look like in their context. Yet, this appreciation did not translate into ownership because the technical and infrastructural requirements for hosting fell outside what counties could realistically manage with existing resources and skills.

UDI should explore whether a tiered hosting strategy: counties with the capacity to host their own dashboards should be supported to do so; counties without that capacity should be offered access to a shared infrastructure managed at the regional or national government level. The intent in both arrangements is to retain county-level access and ownership of the data while matching technical responsibility to county capacity. Adaptation for Cycle 3: Adopt a formal transition plan with capacity-building milestones and an agreed timeline for moving counties from externally hosted dashboards to county-managed or shared-infrastructure hosting. Initiate a feasibility assessment for the shared-hosting option early in the cycle. (See Section 6.2.4 for the operational detail.)

5. Preliminary outcomes and indicators

The findings from Cycle 2 show measurable but uneven progress across the three strategic objectives of the UDI. This section presents preliminary implementation outcomes, situating them within the programme's longer-term goal of sustainable, institutionalised use of data at scale across county government systems.

Cycle 2 does not fully demonstrate institutional change; a single cycle cannot deliver that. What it shows is that the conditions for institutional change are forming. Counties are building data officer structures, beginning to use data in real administrative decisions, and shifting ownership of data systems from programme to county. The three outcomes below trace each of these movements and map them to the strategic objectives set out earlier in the report.

5.1. Leadership as the catalyst: Scaling through institutional anchoring

This finding moves towards scaling data use by addressing the most common reason data use fails to spread beyond individual officers or isolated projects: the absence of institutional structures that outlast any single person or programme cycle. By formalising data officer roles with defined mandates, counties are creating the *infrastructure that enables scale*. Scaling is not simply about more counties doing more with data; it is about building systems where data use is a recognised function of government rather than a personal initiative.

Senior leadership endorsement matters precisely because it accelerates this institutionalisation. When a CECM or senior director publicly endorses data formalisation, it signals across the county system that data use is a governance priority, not a donor preference. This signal normalises data roles and legitimises resource allocation toward them, both of which are preconditions for scale. The Kajiado example described in Section 3.2, where the County Director of Education raised the need for data capacity at the Education TWG and the TWG endorsed the request, illustrates this mechanism in practice.

5.2. From isolated practice to institutional habit: Data use embedded in routine county operations

The most significant shift in data culture observed across counties did not result from training alone. It occurred when officers discovered that data could help them resolve challenges they were already responsible for addressing. In Kisumu, the impetus was not a programme directive to collect land data; it was the practical administrative requirement for ECDE centre registration that made land ownership data immediately relevant. In Kirinyaga, enrollment data proved compelling because it directly answered a deployment question that education officers routinely faced. In Marsabit, the water

tracking survey was driven by the need to make targeted, defensible infrastructure interventions. In each case, data moved from an abstract programme expectation to a concrete operational tool because it was connected to a problem the officer already owned.

5.3. Data systems controlled, maintained and driven by county governments

The genuine ownership finding advances the scaling agenda by addressing the structural vulnerability that most directly undermines the long-term replication of data systems across counties: the reliance on externally managed, technically complex infrastructure that counties can access but cannot control. Without resolving this dependency, every new county brought into the programme inherits the same fragility: systems that function during the programme cycle and deteriorate once external support is withdrawn. The scale built on this foundation is breadth without durability.

Local-capacity alignment lowers the maintenance cost of running a data system; locally generated, contextually relevant data raises the value of using it. Together, these two conditions make counties more likely to invest in maintaining the systems.

In Cycle 2 terms, no county has yet completed the transition to fully county-owned hosting; what the cycle has shown is that the conditions for the transition are forming, with technical solutions matched to county capacity, and that the hosting gap remains the largest open question for Cycle 3.

6. Conclusion and next steps

6.1 Conclusion

Cycle 2 marks a turning point for the programme. The evidence gathered across participating counties demonstrates that the initiative has moved beyond its foundational phase, which focused on introducing data concepts and building basic skills. It has entered a more complex and consequential phase, where the challenge is to embed data use so deeply within county governance structures that it persists and grows independently of programme support.

Three things have to come together for that embedding to hold. First, institutional architecture: formalised roles, senior leadership endorsement, and anchoring in county HR frameworks. Without these, data capacity stays with the individual rather than the county. Second, cultural integration is a shift in how officers relate to data, from a reporting obligation to a tool for work. And underneath both, genuine technical ownership: systems counties can run themselves, not systems they merely access.

Cycle 2 shows progress on all three dimensions. Data officer roles are being formalised across counties. In Kisumu, Kirinyaga, Marsabit, and Kajiado, officers are now using data to inform real administrative decisions. The conversation about technical ownership has moved from whether counties should own their systems to how that ownership can be achieved in practice. This is structural deepening, not incremental improvement, and it gives the programme a credible foundation for scale.

At the same time, the lessons learned in this cycle are candid about the distance that remains. Job descriptions that exist outside official HR frameworks remain fragile. Data culture, while emerging, is uneven across counties and, in many cases, still dependent on the presence of motivated individuals rather than on enabling institutional conditions. The gap between appreciating a dashboard and having the capacity to host it represents a technical ownership challenge that the programme has identified but not yet resolved.

The path from here to sustainable, county-owned data use at scale is therefore neither linear nor guaranteed. It runs through the deliberate consolidation of what Cycle 2 has begun and through the targeted adaptations that the programme's own evidence now makes possible.

6.2 Next Steps

The following priority actions are recommended for Cycle 3, organised around the three strategic objectives and the lessons set out in Section 4.

6.2.1 Institutionalise data roles within official county frameworks

The formalisation of data officer roles must extend beyond programme documentation to official county establishment. In Cycle 3, the programme should work directly with county human resource departments to ensure that data officer job descriptions are formally gazetted, graded, and included in county staff establishment registers. This is the single most important structural action for protecting the investments made in Cycle 2 against the risk of personnel turnover. Alongside this, the TWG terms of reference should be formally adopted within county governance structures, and handover protocols should be tested through at least one documented transition during the cycle.

6.2.2. Activate peer champion networks

Counties where senior officials actively championed data formalisation, and where that championing produced measurable results, represent a programme asset that has not yet been fully leveraged. In Cycle 3, the programme should establish a structured peer-champion network, convening CECM- and director-level officials from high-performing counties for facilitated cross-county learning exchanges. These exchanges should be designed not as showcase events but as working sessions where officials from counties at earlier stages of the journey engage directly with the institutional strategies and personal decisions that drove formalisation elsewhere. Testimonies from peer champions should be documented and packaged for use across the broader county cohort.

6.2.3. Anchor data activities to county planning and budget calendars

To accelerate the adoption of data culture beyond the counties where it has already taken root, Cycle 3 should prioritise aligning all data collection and analysis activities to the administrative moments that matter most in the county calendar, annual work planning, budget consultations, and departmental review meetings. A mapping exercise should be conducted at the start of the cycle with each county to identify these moments and ensure that data is available in the right format and at the right time to inform them. The programme should also develop a core set of replicable use cases, drawn from the Kisumu, Kirinyaga, Marsabit, and Kajiado examples that can be adapted and adopted by counties where data culture is still emerging.

6.2.4. Resolve the hosting gap through a tiered technical strategy

The disconnect between dashboard appreciation and hosting capacity must be addressed as a programme design priority, not an implementation footnote. In Cycle 3, the programme should formally adopt a structured transition plan with a defined timeline and capacity-building milestones, monitored against county capacity assessments. In parallel, the programme should initiate a feasibility assessment for a shared hosting arrangement at the regional or national government level, exploring whether a centrally managed infrastructure could reduce the technical burden on individual counties while preserving county-level data access and ownership.

6.2.5. Strengthen monitoring of cultural and ownership indicators

The programme's monitoring framework should be updated ahead of Cycle 3 to capture the quality of institutional change rather than activity outputs alone. New indicators should track whether data featured in the most recent county annual work plan, whether a budget or deployment decision during the cycle was visibly informed by evidence, and whether data officer roles have been formally adopted into county HR frameworks. These indicators offer a more accurate and meaningful picture of progress toward the UDI long-term outcome than output counts alone.

6.2.6. Document and disseminate the cycle 2 evidence

The findings, use cases, and lessons from Cycle 2 constitute a significant body of practical evidence about what works in building data culture within sub-national government systems in Kenya. This evidence should not remain internal to the programme. A dissemination strategy should be developed to share key findings with national government counterparts, development partners, and other subnational governance programmes operating in comparable contexts. Dissemination channels should include the UDI evidence library, KIX Africa hubs, the Education Deans Forum (Kenya), and the MoE Directorate of Quality Assurance and Standards.

7. References

These references are available digitally in our evidence library at

<https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/GU5WSVPE>

Andrews, M., Pritchett, L., & Woollock, M. (2017). *Building state capability: Evidence, analysis, action*. Oxford University Press. Available from https://academic.oup.com/book/26994?__cf_chl_f_tk=ayF3YHXHTy5NIqDHWE9.eTUvesWebPtO5FxsEJWRPg0-1782819031-1.0.1.1-C5sPd6qcdNVAdQPML18WSriYJXTK4.2YtYQI__X89u8. (details)

Arisa, K., & Gachoki, C. (2025). *Evidence Gap Map Report: Foundational Learning in Kenya* [Evidence Review]. Unlocking data. <https://doi.org/10.53832/unlockingdata.1022>. Available from <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/G4EBJIQ5>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. (details)

Fishman, B. J., Penuel, W. R., Allen, A.-R., Cheng, B. H., & Sabelli, N. (2013). Design-based implementation research: An emerging model for transforming the relationship of research and practice. *Teachers College Record*, 115(14), 136–156. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146811311501415>. Available from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/016146811311501415>. (details)

Gachoki, C., & Arisa, K. (2025). *Exploring the Foundational Learning Data and Knowledge Ecosystem in Sub-Saharan Africa: Kenya's Situational Analysis*. Unlocking Data. <https://doi.org/10.53832/unlockingdata.1003>. Available from <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/THAJ93PC>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. (details)

Gachoki, C., Arisa, K., Mutisya, M., & Karimi, R. (2025). *Design-Based Implementation Research Report: Cycle 1. Increasing Foundational Learning Data Access by Policymakers, Focus on Sub-National Level In Kenya* [Collaborative Evaluation]. Unlocking Data. <https://doi.org/10.53832/unlockingdata.1028>. Available from <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/8CHWSNXQ>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. (details)

Penuel, W. R., Fishman, B. J., Haugan Cheng, B., & Sabelli, N. (2011). Organizing research and development at the intersection of learning, implementation, and design. *Educational Researcher*, 40(7), 331–337. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X11421826>. (details)

Waziri, N. (2026). *An Applied Design-Based Implementation Research Framework for the Unlocking Data Initiative* [Guidance Note]. Unlocking data. <https://doi.org/10.53832/unlockingdata.1043>. Available from <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/6W4M82D5>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. (details)